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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Because You Believed

You taught me how to be an efficient leader
A leader who serves, not one who seeks power
You taught me to do things always with excellence
And even now, it lives in me every hour

At first, I was afraid, unsure of what to do
But you mentored and shaped me to see things through
They told me I would be challenged because it is you
And indeed, it was true, but you guided me through

It is sad when you had to go away
But you prepared us well for another day
Your wisdom stayed and helped me see
The leader I was meant to be

I seldom saw you after college days
But your teachings stayed in countless ways
They humbled me and taught me what is right
To lead with courage, truth, and light

I remember how you pushed me to my limits each time
I remember how you stood for me when judgment was mine
You saw something in me I could not yet see
And fought for the person I was meant to be

Your legacy will always stay with me
Your teachings will shape who I will be
They will still touch lives, far and wide
And carry your vision with quiet pride